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HOW DIGITAL MARKETING AND PERCEIVED PERFORMANCE ARE INFLUENCING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

Currently, digital marketing has become an essential factor in campaigns to attract and retain online buyers. This study aims to identify how different digital marketing tools impact consumer buying behaviour. This research shows the most appropriate actions to take while planning an online strategy and retaining users. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of perceived performance in shaping consumer behaviour, as consumers are more likely to purchase if they believe that a product or service meets their expectations. Also, this research signifies running an effective digital marketing campaign. This research has implications for businesses looking to improve their marketing strategies and enhance their customer relationships in the digital age. Non-probability sampling method was used to select the sample. Convenience sampling involves selecting participants who are easily accessible and willing to participate in the study. The data is gathered through online surveys from a sample of 450 respondents. To analyze the data, the study used SPSS software and Smart PLS. SPSS is a statistical software package used for data analysis. The conclusion of this research shows factors that should be utilized while planning a campaign with digital marketing tools. The effect on Consumer buying behaviour for online purchases is necessary for all SMEs, e-commerce, and online retail industries, especially their performance. Through this research, companies can identify which campaign is suitable for them to run in the market of Karachi. A full detailed study is required by having different performance indicators as mediators or moderators in the future.

Key Words: Digital marketing, consumer buying behaviour, perceived performance, digital channels, consumer online purchase behaviour

Introduction

Scholars have studied the function of digital marketing in-depth for the past three decades.

However, current research is mostly concerned with the function and effects of digital marketing in business-to-consumer (B2C) settings (Kim & Moon, 2021). The recent advancement of social platforms is one of the most significant changes in how people connect. This study aims to study how digital marketing affects consumer behaviour in the expanding online purchasing industry. We'll also learn how the effectiveness of each digital platform affects consumers' decisions to shop online.

The emergence of the internet and the digital economy of business in past recent years has forced a reconsidering of marketing tactics and, utmost of all, the purchasing habits of consumers by granting individuals access to global content, the ability to produce content, the ability to access Spreading infrastructure for consumer-generated media, and the ability to access viewer (Tiewul, 2020). The internet has greatly benefited communication, sharing knowledge, and encouraging individual creativity and invention.

More than seventy per cent of the population of Pakistan uses a digital or net platform to access the internet and social platform to stay in touch with close ones. As a result, digital marketing is the starting point for any business looking to enter the Pakistani market and boost online sales and leads (*Scope of Digital Marketing in Pakistan - Digital Marketing Pakistan*, n.d.). Today, many people use social sites, media platforms, smartphone apps, and other digital communication technologies regularly. For illustration, 37% of individuals in Pakistan currently use the internet.

Digital marketing is also helpful for online customer purchases because it may be a source for

Products that are available online and that customers may like to choose and follow up on. Digital marketing also served as a platform for images, videos, and customer testimonials about their experiences using products and services. Social media gives information about all customers extremely clearly; therefore, using it would transform how people explore information about products or services.

For businesses to effectively compete in the new 2.0 & 3.0 marketplaces, ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) have been incorporated into all of these contemporary marketing techniques.

This technical business perspective can help micro, small, and medium-sized businesses

Modernize, obtain the tools they need to establish a lasting position in the market, particularly in the 2.0 and 3.0 sectors, and successfully identify their customers online. In fact, by 2017, digital channels are expected to make a claim approximately one-third of global advertising expenditure (Stephen, 2016).

The impact of digital marketing on Pakistan's major cities was investigated in this study. The purchasing habits of Karachi residents are studied when they make direct or online purchases. The segments that follow will go over the study's theoretical foundation, methods, findings, discussions, and conclusions.

Research Objectives:

- To measure changes in consumer purchasing patterns caused by digital marketing technologies.
- To assess which digital marketing platform is most effective at altering consumer behaviour.
- To understand the behaviour of online buyers by perceived performance.

Problem statement

This study's main objective is to determine how digital marketing affects consumers' purchasing behaviours. An increasingly common channel for brand and consumer involvement over the past few years has been digital marketing. To serve customers and advertise goods and services, marketing experts have used a variety of media for years. The performance of those platforms is crucial since digital marketing also serves as a route for online purchases. With a focus on consumer time and security, we must examine what motivates customers to shop online and how any digital marketing agency may enhance its performance to attract more users as customers on online platforms. We can considerably understand consumer buying behaviour online by analyzing the performance impact of each digital marketing instrument.

Literature Review

On the ground of digital marketing, there are multiple reasons to do research. This topic is very challenging, has a wide scope and implies unique techniques or simply it is an extensive, exclusive, and thought-provoking topic. Despite not knowing where or how to start, businesses are looking for a more defined beginning point for their digital marketing initiatives. Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Google, and other businesses have been effective in modifying consumer viewpoints and attitudes in the contemporary era, which has ultimately changed many enterprises. A sizable, comprehensive customer network, trustworthy data, and real-time customer experience feedback were used to achieve this.

A transition in marketing from traditional to digital

The development of technology is intrinsically related to the expansion of digital marketing. The first email was sent in 1971 by

Ray Tomlinson, and this innovation created the framework for enabling users to send and receive files across various machines. The phrase "digital marketing" was first used and became well-known in the 1990s. Between 1994 and 1996, the number of internet users increased from 16 to 70 million due to consumers purchasing personal computers and using email.

The broad consensus is that large corporations, like Apple and Amazon, are reaping all the advantages that digital technologies can provide, whereas small or local businesses find it difficult to gain in any way (Makrides et al., 2020). Online surveys which are conducted for companies and organizations are substantially more practical for use to collect relevant information from certain target audiences and analyze the outcomes based on their responses. To choose sensibly whether to purchase a good or use a service, potential customers usually check for its reviews and recommendation. On either hand, companies practice pertinent online customer feedback to understand their customers' demands better.

Setting a goal to increase brand awareness abroad through the use of digital marketing strategies necessitates the development of a well-thought-out strategy that can successfully take advantage of new technical developments.

For businesses that use it, digital marketing offers five significant benefits.

- First, both big and small businesses can do this.
- Second, comparing the advertising space to print and broadcast media, there are no real restrictions.
- Third, compared to express mail or even faxes, information access and search are fairly quick.
- Fourth, people in any corner of the world can have access to a website with no time restrictions.

- Fifth, the span for doing shopping and research is likely reduces and can be done efficiently.

The attributes of digital marketing as it relates to promotion as a component of the marketing mix (4Ps). Despite the posters' positive product experiences and dedication to these, these effects persisted (Schlosser, 2005) there are Website, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Paid Search Click-based Advertising (PPC advertising), Affiliate marketing, and strategic partnerships (affiliate marketing and strategic partnership), online public relations (Online PR), social networks (social networks), Email marketing (Email marketing), Customer relationship management (Customer Relationship Management. In addition, digital marketing has SMM, Mobile marketing, Content marketing and management, and Marketing analytics. The study makes an effort to thoroughly investigate the relationship between each aspect of the digital marketing tool and Consumer behaviour on its own. Contrarily, several hypotheses have advocated undertaking additional research to comprehend the behaviour all aims of people like the CBB.

Consumer Behavior towards Online Shopping

Consumer behaviour studies how people make purchasing or buying decisions. It makes an effort to understand the various phases people take before making a purchase as well as by what method consumers select, use, and abandon a product and a service. Consumer behaviour is also known as how consumers' state of mind, attitudes, and preferences are affecting their purchasing decisions.

Considering the innumerable consumer types and their distinct purchasing behaviours grounded on their involvement with the purchasing process, their capacity to recognize and awareness of how consumers behave while making purchases necessitates

knowledge of important brand differences. (Hawkins, 2012) Says as the level of interest a consumer has in purchasing a good or service, the phrase "buying engagement" might be used.

(Kotler P. a., 2011) Give the following description of Assael's model of the many customer purchase choice behaviour types:

1. Complex buying behaviour - this term describes consumers who are highly involved in the purchasing or buying process and who can discern substantial brand distinctions.
2. Dissonance-reducing buying behaviour - describes consumers who are very involved in the purchasing process but who are unable to distinguish meaningful distinctions between brands.
3. Habitual purchasing behaviour - This relates to consumers' nonengagement in the purchase and their incapacity to recognize significant brand differences.
4. Variety-seeking purchasing behaviour - describes customers' minimal purchase engagement and their capacity to recognize substantial variations between the products.

Influence on Buyer decisions is due to several important cultural, psychological, social, and personal factors. Demographics, social groupings including families and friends, and media influence on consumer behaviour are all examined in consumer behaviour research.

Previous studies have shown that even a small number of unfavourable reviews can significantly influence consumer purchasing behaviour and choice (Schlosser, 2005). This is because a consumer may create a fundamental link with other buyers. As a result, consumers increasingly rely on social media networks and websites to gather information about products before making a decision (Rasmunder, 2011).

When social media networking and websites are changing consumer perception, we will analyze the result of overall Digital marketing tools over a consumer.

Habitual buying behaviour relates to consumers' limited buying engagement and inability to recognize important brand differences. Or in other words Habitual purchasing - little or no customer interaction, regular purchases, and brand distinction (Ramo Palalic, 2020).

In these circumstances, consumer behaviour does not follow the typical belief-attitude-behaviour chain. The consumer does not conduct in-depth research, weigh brand attributes, and make significant selections over "which brand to buy." Customers or buyers do not have strong brand loyalty. Price and sales incentives or discounts are frequently used by marketers of low-effort products with few brand variations to encourage purchasing.

It's crucial to first comprehend the idea of habitual purchasing to comprehend how digital marketing and customer behaviour are related. The act of routinely buying a good or service is known as habitual buying, and it is frequently motivated by an emotional connection to a brand. Over time, consumers will buy things because they have become emotionally attached to them. In other words, customers are more inclined to keep buying a brand's items if they are already familiar with them.

This idea can be utilized in a broad range of ways in terms of digital marketing. For instance, customers may start to favour particular online brand advertisements over others if they get used to seeing them. Promoting discounts or other incentives that are only valid if a customer uses an online payment method, this kind of advertising can also be used to encourage consumers to make purchases.

When discussing customer behaviour in online marketing, complicated buying should also be taken into account in addition to habitual purchasing. When customers look for several different sorts of things at once, this is called complex buying (e.g., groceries and clothing).

Customers act in this way while making expensive, infrequently purchased purchases. Before making a high-value investment, consumers actively participate in the purchasing process and research. A complex purchasing behaviour might be buying a home or an automobile. Consumers' high purchase engagement and capacity to recognize key brand differences are referred to as complex buying behaviour (Palalic et al., 2021).

In complex purchasing, the customer will go through a learning method where they initially form their opinion about the product, then consider its attributes, and finally make a learnt purchase decision (Kotler P., 1991).

When customers fully participate in the decision-making cycle, complex buying behaviour is at stake. What customers must do to comprehend an interesting product is stated as "involvement". A high level of participation, which is characteristic among auto or vehicle buyers, indicates that the individual makes a great effort to comprehend the product. The decision's inherent characteristics are what motivate this conduct.

First of all, complicated items are costly. High involvement stems from this.

Second, complicated transactions involve powerful emotions and a strong sense of commitment.

Third, large transactions require a lot of personal information. Consumers associate the cost of a complex buy with the time and effort put into making it since it is pricey.

Fourth, complicated purchases don't happen frequently. The typical consumer

views their purchases as occurring in a predictable monthly cycle.

Fifth, complicated purchases are unfamiliar in addition to being unusual.

Lastly, it's rare for one person to make a complicated purchase decision. No matter how many reviews and ratings a dealership receives, sellers and marketers are constantly bombarded with information. The degree of knowledge a consumer has gained from other people's experiences influences how easily they can make complex purchases.

Dissonance is defined as "a disagreement of people's beliefs, acts, or characters" in the dictionary. In a similar vein, worry after purchases can be understood as dissonance-reducing buying.

Consumers are very invested in their purchases, but they struggle to distinguish different brands.

Consumers may experience "dissonance" if they second-guess their decision after the fact. Products from the financial services industry, such as insurance, and investments, are some examples. Every brand's marketing strategy has been built on a thorough understanding of customer behaviour, and for an organization to succeed, a thorough investigation of all its facets is now necessary. Thus, cognitive dissonance and its effect on consumer behaviour have also been covered in numerous important research articles or papers (Sharma, 2014).

An author referred to it as one of social psychology's most important theories (Aronson 1969). Dissonance, according to (Sweeney, 2000) both a cognitive feature, as implied by the title cognitive dissonance, as well as an emotional component, as suggested by several definitions, including Festinger's original definition.

Such products will be selected by consumers based on their cost or convenience, and they will search for

additional assurance for the decision they are making for the purchase is right.

Dissonance-reducing purchasing behaviour is the result of consumers' intense involvement in the purchase process and their inability to discern distinguishing features between brands (Palalic et al., 2021).

The significance of cognitive dissonance.

Numerous value assessments, choices, and evaluations are influenced by cognitive dissonance. You can greatly enhance your capacity to make quicker and more accurate decisions by gaining awareness of how opposing philosophies affect the decision-making process.

Individuals' propensity to seek variety in the services or products they purchase is known as variety-seeking in purchase behaviour. Such variation could develop over time, for example, when a customer picks various restaurants throughout a series of session occasions.

Individuals that engage in variety-seeking behaviour in their consumption will avoid having their utility decline as a result of making the same purchases or utilizing the same products again, switching brands, types, or objects. (Ratner, 1999). People frequently move between options or choose numerous options from a decision set over time (Shaddy, 2021). Variety-seeking behaviour in the marketing field also includes varying between marketing efforts and offerings. Even though customers can regularly purchase their favourite products from a specific selection set, prior research indicated that consumers buy a certain number of diversified products (Ratner, 1999).

When a consumer selects a portfolio of products, variety may also be a crucial factor. For instance, when making a decision, Customers may have used financial services or investments. Customers want to pick a broad portfolio.

(McAlister, 1982) Categorized different behaviours in variety seeking are derived or direct. Derived variety-seeking conduct, or activity not directly related to a need for variety, was the outcome of another incentive. Numerous requirements, numerous users, or numerous circumstances led to this kind of variety-seeking. Direct activity motivated by intrapersonal goals was described as variety-seeking behaviour:

Variety-seeking is motivated by a need for novelty, change, or satiation with a product's features.

Three primary elements are identified in the research today as driving variety-seeking behaviour. In line with the (McAlister, 1982) direct variety-seeking theory, the first factor describes how customers actively seek out diversity for their reasons. To clarify what triggers the desire for variety, we refer to this form of motivation for variety-seeking as satiation/stimulation.

The second factor is outside circumstances, which is related to the derived variety-seeking of (McAlister, 1982).

Under these circumstances, consumers look for diversity because of external constraints rather than an immediate internal demand for variation. The third incentive, which we refer to as future preference uncertainty, is another that does not appear in the (McAlister, 1982) paradigm. The above discussion told us about so many things which impact consumer variety-seeking perspective, and digital online platforms can influence it through daily updates and trending variety of products or services.

Perceived performance in digital marketing

In the digital marketing spectrum, performance has a different meaning and depends upon consumer events, usage experience, and quality spent time on that specific platform. A subjective indicator of the functionality, responsiveness, and dependability of a website is perceived

performance. In other words, the speed is perceived by the user of a website. After Information technology induction in market and marketing strategies, these performance levels do not remain only to calculate profit and loss margins.

The theory of UTAUT was used to examine the factors that led to the acceptance of mobile or smartphone apps. The findings confirmed the value of routine, hedonic motivation, social influence, and performance expectations (Mütterlein, 2019).

Perceived Performance first checks the effectiveness and ineffectiveness of an objective or approach to run on a specific platform.

The web performance community used Page Load Time (onLoad) and a few other page-level navigation metrics in the past for assessing the performance (QoE) of a website. According to (Gao et al., 2017) According to a common industry orthodoxy, the smaller these measurements, given the same network conditions, content organization, and other controllable characteristics, the better the quality of experience of a webpage will be (from the end-user viewpoint).

These researches were only for web pages, but after the social era, things behaved differently because of the expansion of Digital platforms.

Various digital marketing tools and platforms have their performance level and uniqueness. Load time in a webpage can affect the website, resulting in negative performance. These negative factors can decrease ranking, increase bounce rate, and ultimately the purpose of SEO and PPC diminish. All other factors can increase and decrease a user's or consumer's perceived performance.

Accessibility on all platforms should be simple for all users, and broadband speed is important. Digital perceived performance includes consumer experience in online

banking, digital checkouts, and other digital services like ordering food, getting ride-hailing services, online shopping, and more.

In this research, we are finding the facts about consumer behaviour and digital marketing which are impacted by performance.

Hypothesis:

In the evidence of the above literature review following is the hypothesis which is formed by the author:

- H1:** Digital marketing (DM) has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour (CBB)
- H2:** Mobile Marketing (MM) has a positive impact on Consumer Buying Behavior (CBB).
- H3:** Social media marketing (SMM) has a positive impact on Consumer buying behaviour (CBB).
- H4:** Pay-per-click (PPC) advertising has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour (CBB)
- H5:** Search Engine Optimization (SEO) has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour (CBB)
- H6:** Email marketing (EM) has a positive impact on Consumer buying behaviour (CBB)
- H7:** Consumer buying behaviour is positively influenced by digital marketing tools.
- H8:** If perceived performance (PP) is effective then digital marketing (DM) tools will be more effective.
- H9:** Perceived performance (PP) influences the relationship between Digital marketing (DM) and consumer buying behaviour (CBB)

Methodology

Research Approach

This research is a combination of exploratory and Descriptive research, as some variables are unstructured, and the suggestion was so important in data collection. Using primary data, this research

employs qualitative and quantitative for gathering data. This is mostly because it sparked research into the causal connections between variables to consumer behaviour in comparison to digital marketing and their perceived performance in Karachi.

With a limited sample size, the qualitative research approach conducts an exploratory study to better understand the issue at hand. Data is gathered using a variety of methods, including observations, open-ended questionnaires, and interviews. These methods aid the researcher in collecting replies to research questions which are based on the respondents' reflections on their expressions of emotions and experiences related to the issue (O'Gorman, 2015)

The study's primary goal is to evaluate consumer purchasing patterns to digital marketing when those campaigns perform poorly with consumers who use or shop online. The study's main goal is to gather information and generalize findings from a wide sample of the population. As a result, it emphasizes completing a structured questionnaire with formal questions asked in a precise order and structured response options.

Whereas on our variables like Digital marketing and CBB consumer buying behaviour, research has already taken place, but we are applying it to an exploratory variable, so questions driven from both are interlinked with descriptive and exploratory and their correlation over each other. This research has a proposition of scientific knowledge and business sciences thus, the approach of this research is Basic. Its theoretical base and theories which are being used in this research are UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology), TAM (technology acceptance model), and CBB (consumer buying behaviour).

Measures of Constructs

Digital marketing measurements were modified from (Tiago & Veríssimo, 2014) based on nine different attributes of the online or digital presence of people on social media, search engine ads, emails, mobile applications, mobile marketing and their behaviour with online advertisement. Second, consumer buying behaviour (CBB) was analyzed (Verplanken & Herabadi, 2001).

Consisting of seven constructs mainly focused on buyers' behaviour towards each online platform, their buying consistency, their ease of shopping, and their satisfaction with digital purchases. The idea for the third measure, Perceived performance, was taken from (Tran et al., 2019), which has seven questions analyzing customer experience with online performance, their reaction to speed and interface while using any application, devices they feel easy to use while purchasing online stuff and for discussion, we asked for their feedback that what can improve customer experience by digital buying.

Sampling Technique

According to the (worldpopulationreview, 2022) world population review, it is estimated that the population of Karachi is 17.6 Million. And in the report of statistics of Pakistan (statista, 2021), it is concluded that 60% of the population is lying between the age bracket of 15-64.

It is also stated in a report published by "date reported (Digital 2022: Pakistan, 2022)" that around 40% of the population is lying between 18-44.

In another report of date reported (Digital 2022: Pakistan, 2022), it is stated that 36.5 per cent of the total population is using the internet.

Therefore, according to facts and figures, the total population size for this research is probably 2.5 million.

The stratified Random Sampling technique is used for the Overall population.

The target audience is stratified into five subgroups which is their area of living. The researcher chose District East, District West, District South, District Central and Malir District and questionnaires were spread in each district. The idea behind choosing these districts is that these areas have the most coverage of the city.

Research Design

The questionnaire is created in such a way that responders would find it engaging and simple to understand. Additionally, only relevant information was acquired via the questionnaire, which only contained the questions needed to accomplish the goals of the study.

The questionnaire was prepared with the support of the research supervisor. The language which is used in the questionnaire is English for the targeted group of people. The questionnaire was created in such a way that it will be confidential, and people who fill that out will stay anonymous. This allowed respondents to remain anonymous and avoid personal identification.

The questionnaire followed a specific framework and included several types of questions. The first part of the questionnaire is to collect demographic containing age, gender, educational level (EL), area of living, and in a multiple-choice format. The second part is for the use of Digital Marketing for online purchases in respondents' daily routines. The third part was to collect Consumer behaviour toward behaviour towards different online channels. Last and fourth we obtained their response on the Perceived performance of digital marketing which respondents are using and what are the most sources they used for their online purchases.

Data Collection

The questionnaire was used for data collection. Every survey was conducted online via Google Forms. The five-point Likert scale,

which is strongly agreed to strongly disagree, includes 4 parts. The age range of the study's target population is 18 to 40. There are differences in Gen Y members' educational levels and access use of digital marketing. As a result, discrepancies between age groups will exist depending on the greatest level of education, gender, and occupation (Noble et al., 2009).

Given that the target audience for this study is young adults, a self-administered pen-paper intercept and online forms survey was judged appropriate (De Vries & Carlson, 2014). Respondents were also approached through online surveys and personal interviews. Only those respondents were allowed who are likely to use online channels to buy stuff online.

The questionnaire was spread among 600 people between the period of august 2022 and November 2022. In that period author received 492 responses of which 458 were selected for data analysis.

Software

SPSS software and Smart PLS 4 (Ringle, 2022) were used to check confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The PLS-SEM model is used to check outer loading and discriminant values of collected responses. Data from SPSS that has been abstracted is then imported into an excel document to produce pie charts and bar diagrams for better presentation.

Data Analysis Technique:

For descriptive statistics, SPSS software is used, and to analyze inferential statistics researchers used Smarts. For all direct models, SPSS analytics is used. Hypothesis test runs are performed with the same tool.

In SPSS linear equation model is used to run hypothesis and correlation formation. For analyzing data, the author uses PLS-SEM, and for the calculation, the researcher uses a consistent PLS algorithm technique.

The measurement model was reflective, and SmartPLS was used to examine all exterior

loadings. The Cronbach's alpha and Construct reliability and validity are also determined by the same program. In this study, Cronbach's alpha exceeds 0.70, which is beyond the permissible range of 0.70 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981a). The acceptance rate of composite reliability is 0.60; the three variables in this research have Composite Reliability between the ranges of 0.71 to 0.748, which is a good result. Following data analysis, the average variance value was determined (AVE) was less than 0.50 in 2 variables, but according to (Fornell & Larcker, 1981b) that if composite reliability is higher than 0.60 then the value of AVE less than 0.5 is acceptable, which indicates that this model has accurate reliability and validity.

Results and Findings

The model is driven by Smart PLS 4.0.

The reflecting model, which shows how each variable is related, is drawn from Smart PLS version 4. PP (perceived performance), DM (Digital Marketing), and CBB (Consumer buying behaviour). The R square of CBB is 0.639, and the R square of DM is 0.624, showing a good relationship.

Demographic Information:

Age of Respondent		
	Frequency	Per cent
18-24	256	55.90%
25-30	154	33.6%
31-39	48	10.5%
Total	458	100%

Gender		
	Frequency	Per cent
Male	254	55.5%
Female	204	44.5%
Total	458	100%
Education Level		
	Frequency	Per cent
Matric	20	4.4%
Intermediate	106	23.1%
Bachelor's Degree	170	37.1%
Master's Degree	144	31.4%
Professional Certification	18	3.9%
Total	458	100%
Occupation		
	Frequency	Per- cent
Employed full time	232	50.7%
Self Employed	56	12.25
A Housewife	28	6.1%
A Student	142	31%
Total	458	100%
Do you buy things over the internet?		
	Frequency	Per cent
Yes	408	89.1%
No	50	10.9%
Total	458	100%

In this research, the data is collected from 17% of district malir, 15% from district ease, 36% from district central, 15% from district west, and the remaining from district south. The researcher analyzed that 48% plus respondents are buying products from online channels every month, and 37% are utilizing this channel once or twice a year.

Discriminant Validity

In the Discriminant validity of this paper, the author has analyzed a strong relationship between DM and CBB of 0.8, with PP and CBB having a positive relation of 0.644. PP and DM

relationship is high with a value of 0.786. Between Digital marketing, perceived performance, and consumer buying behaviour there is a positive correlation. HTMT matrix is used for correlation for different variables.

	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
DM-> CBB	0.800
PP-> CBB	0.644
PP-> DM	0.786
PP x DM-> CBB	0.326
PP x DM-> DM	0.410
PP x DM-> PP	0.607

Construct Reliability and Validity

The most crucial factors in determining if a question is relevant are its validity and reliability. Those questions are used in the measurement of correlations and other examinations of data. In this research AVE in two variables is less than 0.5, as explained in the methodology if Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability is greater than 0.6 in this situation Average variance extracted is acceptable at a level of 0.4.

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	The average variance extracted (AVE)
C				
B	0.750	0.752	0.748	0.427
D	0.735	0.745	0.736	0.418
P	0.709	0.712	0.710	0.551

Summary of results

Proposed Paths	Pearson's Correlation	p-values	Hypotheses
H1: DM ---> CBB	0.412	0.00	Supported
H2: MM --> CBB	0.215	0.00	Supported
H3: SMM --> CBB	0.521	0.00	Supported
H4: PPC --> CBB	0.321	0.00	Supported
H5: SEO --> CBB	0.382	0.00	Supported

H6: EM --> CBB	0.042	0.00	Unsupported
H7: CBB --> DMT	0.488	0.00	Supported
H8: PP --> DM	0.932	0.00	Supported
H9: DM x CBB --> PP	0.326	-	Supported

Discussion

This study is for a specific geographic region and the central idea of this research is to conclude how consumer behaviour is being changed by different digital marketing tools and if the perceived performance of those tools gets better, how will this impact consumer buying behaviour.

Karachi is one of the most populated cities in the world, with internet users thirty-six per cent and in this figure, around 82% of people are those who have purchased any kind of product or service through online stores. This research is based on a small group of people but if we look at overall factors, there are 17.6 million people who have the potential to buy stuff online.

From the authors' point of view, the purpose of this research met its objectives and this study is conducted successfully. The finding of Karachi cannot cover the population of the whole city but in different areas and different age groups, it is clear that digital marketing and its performance is affecting consumer buying behaviour.

It is also clear that email marketing is not suitable for this audience because it is forming low relations among each other.

From asking people their opinion on better performance of the online channel, they recommended that by having multiple payment methods, making it more user-friendly, integrating it with different social platforms, and adding video teasers and genuine reviews of the product, buyers will be more attracted towards online marketing.

Recommendation

The majority of the population is buying Apparel, fashion accessories, groceries, and

food through the online channel so those SMEs who are newly entering this industry have a good scope and market. For those marketing agencies which are in the market and working on inbound campaigns, this research will help them to analyze the best audience to target from specific online mediums.

This research can also be used from the company's perspective, and that will signify how digital marketing channels are helping their business and what performance indicators can be improvised for more customer buying. For the B2B market, data should be collected in qualitative form purely for better ideas.

Limitations

This research is limited to the boundaries of Karachi. A full detailed study is required by having different performance indicators as mediators or moderators in the future.

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